

uPcycle

National

Phosphorus Action Planning

A framework for addressing the global phosphorus challenge to protect rivers, lakes and coastlines

An uPcycle guidance document – www.upcyclelakes.org

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National Phosphorus Action Planning

A Framework for addressing the global phosphorus challenge to protect
rivers, lakes and coastlines

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Purpose and Scope

The uPcycle Framework for National Phosphorus Action Planning provides a practical approach for developing National Phosphorus Action Plans that support sustainable phosphorus management. Phosphorus is essential for plant growth and food production. However, when fertilisers, manure and wastewater are not managed effectively, phosphorus can enter rivers, lakes and coastal waters, leading to eutrophication, ecosystem degradation and loss of vital water services. A sustainable solution lies in developing circular phosphorus systems that use phosphorus more efficiently, minimise losses and recycle unavoidable waste back into agriculture.

This high-level document provides a framework to help governments and national authorities develop these plans. It outlines how to structure national planning and coordination and focuses on the key actions needed for sustainable phosphorus use. A complementary Monitoring and Assessment Approach supports implementation by explaining how to measure progress, evaluate results and adapt actions as needed. Together, they provide a structured process for national phosphorus management.

The document explains the phosphorus challenge, outlines principles for sustainable phosphorus management and provides practical guidance for action. It helps readers understand how phosphorus moves through catchments and how management strategies can support both agricultural production and healthy ecosystems while minimising pollution.

How this document supports your work

- **Break down complex challenges** – provides clear, actionable guidance to help you address phosphorus management challenges in practical steps.
- **Develop effective strategies** – supports the development of approaches to use phosphorus efficiently for food production while preventing it from becoming pollution.
- **Engage stakeholders** – offers approaches informed by input from communities, policymakers and experts to support practical, adaptable solutions.
- **Apply lessons from global practice** – highlights relevant approaches such as the UN Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 6 Global Accelerator Framework and Integrated Lake Basin Management.

What's inside

- **Part 1: Background and policy context**
Overview of phosphorus pollution, its impacts on lakes and freshwater ecosystems and the key global and national policy frameworks guiding action.
- **Part 2: Principles for integrated phosphorus management**
Introduces the core principles of sustainable and circular phosphorus management, including nutrient circularity, cross-sector integration, systems thinking and long-term stewardship.
- **Part 3: National phosphorus action planning framework**
A step-by-step framework for developing phosphorus action plans centred on the restoration and protection of healthy aquatic ecosystems, ensuring actions support food production while minimising environmental harm.

This document was developed through the uPcycle project, funded by the Global Environment Facility (GEF) in coordination with the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). It is designed to be used alongside the uPcycle Monitoring and Assessment Approach.

By following this guidance, lake managers and stakeholders can save time, reduce uncertainty and implement more effective, science-based strategies to restore and protect ecosystems while ensuring phosphorus is used efficiently in food production.

Note: This version of the framework is presented as a working discussion document. It will be reviewed and refined through engagement with the global community of practice and in collaboration with the Ministry of the Environment of Chile at the conclusion of the uPcycle project.

1

The global phosphorus crisis

A nexus of global challenges

Sustainable phosphorus management is key to addressing four global challenges: food security, water security, climate change and economic stability.

Phosphorus sits at the nexus of food security, water security, climate change and economic stability. Phosphorus is vital for food production, but losses from farms, cities, industries (such as food processing, mining and chemical manufacturing), wastewater and aquaculture can deliver excess phosphorus into water bodies¹. Lakes are especially at risk, as they accumulate phosphorus losses from the land, which can lead to persistent toxic algal blooms that damage ecosystems, drinking water supplies and fisheries². Toxic algal blooms can also contribute to greenhouse gas emissions, linking phosphorus pollution to climate change³. At the same time, climate change can further increase the frequency and intensity of algal blooms by raising water temperatures and altering rainfall patterns, which affect phosphorus runoff and water circulation (**Figure 1**). These consequences extend beyond local ecosystems and economies, as phosphorus-related pollution can also undermine regional food security, exacerbate public health risks and contribute to broader environmental degradation, making the crisis a critical issue for sustainable development worldwide^{4,5}.

Figure 1. Phosphorus mismanagement contributes to three of the planet’s greatest environmental and social challenges. The top row illustrates the challenge areas, while the boxes below highlight key mechanisms that link phosphorus mismanagement to food security, water security and climate change.

Circular phosphorus systems

Transitioning to circular phosphorus systems lies at the heart of the solution for enhancing food security, environmental protection, climate mitigation and socio-economic resilience.

Addressing phosphorus challenges across food production, water quality, waste management, climate and biodiversity requires a shift from linear, resource-intensive approaches to circular systems that recover, reuse and redistribute phosphorus efficiently across the entire nutrient cycle⁶⁻⁹.

Avoiding and capturing phosphorus losses before they cause environmental harm and recycling them back into agricultural production to reduce dependence on phosphate rock, represents a ‘win-win’ strategy to reduce national phosphorus vulnerability^{7,10} (**Figure 2**). This approach also supports the transition towards a circular economy, where economic growth is decoupled from finite resource consumption¹¹.

Despite advances in phosphorus recycling, currently less than 1% of secondary phosphorus resources produced globally are recycled¹². This represents a major opportunity, as manure (15–20 million tons of phosphorus (Mt P) per year), mining and fertiliser industry waste (6–12 Mt P per year), wastewater (~3.7 Mt P per year) and food waste (~1.2 Mt P per year) are available as secondary phosphorus sources worldwide¹². Unlocking these resources improves nutrient security and creates economic value.

Integrated strategies across the phosphorus cycle can reduce environmental losses, improve resource efficiency and support sustainable food production ^{10,13}. Manure processing captures nutrients from livestock operations, reducing runoff and supplying recycled phosphorus for crops ¹⁴. Wastewater treatment recovers phosphorus before it reaches rivers and lakes, improving water quality and providing nutrients for fertiliser production ¹⁵. Precision fertiliser application matches inputs to crop demand, lowering environmental losses and reducing costs for farmers ¹⁶. Circular bioeconomy pathways, including the use of organic waste streams for biogas or compost, add value while returning phosphorus to soils. Together, these strategies also support climate mitigation by reducing greenhouse gas emissions from algal blooms, fertiliser production and organic waste decomposition. At a broader scale, coordinated catchment- or basin-level management integrates these approaches across landscapes, optimising nutrient flows and minimising environmental impacts.

Successful implementation requires collaboration across agriculture, industry, water utilities, regulators, researchers and local communities (Cordell et al., 2021). Such integrated approaches reflect global best practice, aligning with systems-based acceleration promoted by the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 6 Global Acceleration Framework (UN-Water, 2020) and basin-scale governance principles in Integrated Lake Basin Management (ILBM) (ILEC, 2005). Transitioning to a circular phosphorus system provides a unifying foundation for global food security, environmental protection, climate mitigation and long-term socio-economic resilience.

National Phosphorus Action Plans provide a framework for coordinated action to reduce phosphate dependence, improve efficiency and recover nutrients ^{9,13,17}. Despite these opportunities, current phosphorus mismanagement continues to impose substantial costs across economies and ecosystems worldwide.

Figure 2. Potential benefits of a circular phosphorus cycle. Transitioning to a circular phosphorus system can enhance soil fertility, improve nutrient use efficiency, reduce dependence on finite phosphate rock, protect water quality, support climate mitigation, strengthen governance and stakeholder engagement and create economic opportunities. In addition, it will support national to global ambitions on nutrient sustainability (not listed in figure).

Socio-economic costs

Phosphorus mismanagement drives substantial but often poorly quantified socio-economic costs, including billions spent annually on water treatment and ecosystem restoration, while freshwater ecosystem services valued at around USD 2.8 trillion per year are increasingly at risk.

Phosphorus mismanagement imposes major socio-economic costs across multiple sectors, including water management, agriculture, climate mitigation and ecosystem protection. Billions of dollars are spent annually on water treatment, ecosystem restoration and managing harmful algal blooms², yet the full impacts are rarely addressed or compensated. Accurately assessing the full socio-economic impacts is difficult because no standard methodology exists. **Table 1** provides example cost assessments for documented eutrophication events, although these represent only a small fraction of blooms. Algal blooms and their impacts are often poorly managed, leaving society to bear the costs through losses in the ecosystem services on which it depends. These impacts disproportionately affect low-income and vulnerable populations who are least able to cope with the consequences of phosphorus pollution¹⁸.

Freshwater systems are particularly vulnerable to phosphorus pollution. Lakes, reservoirs and their catchments provide essential ecosystem services including fisheries, drinking water, recreation and biodiversity, while supporting local economies. The global value of lake ecosystem services alone is estimated at approximately US\$2.8 trillion per year (Kubiszewski et al., 2017). Without effective management, phosphorus-driven degradation is expected to worsen. By 2050, ecosystem service values could decline by up to 20%¹⁹, nutrient pollution from agriculture and wastewater could at least double^{20,21} and hundreds of billions of dollars per year may be required for remediation⁵. Methane emissions from lakes are projected to increase, with global societal costs in the trillions⁴ and biodiversity loss is expected to accelerate²⁰.

Phosphorus scarcity and price volatility pose risks to agricultural productivity. Smallholder farmers, particularly in lower-income countries, often struggle to afford fertilisers, reducing crop yields and contributing to food insecurity^{22,23}. The global demand for phosphorus is expected to double by 2050²⁴, driven by the global need for food and non-food products, many of which are destined for international trade²⁵. However, phosphorus is a finite resource, and, in a business-as-usual scenario, global phosphorus demand is projected to exceed supply by 2040²⁶. This rising demand, coupled with unsustainable phosphorus use, will place additional strain on ecosystems and economies, making effective phosphorus management even more critical. Among these impacts, risks to food production and fertiliser access are among the most immediate and globally significant.

Table 1. Illustrative examples of harmful algal blooms and eutrophication events worldwide, showing primary nutrient sources, observed impacts, management responses and estimated costs. Estimated costs represent a mix of documented event costs, projected economic damages and annual management or restoration investments. For Chesapeake Bay*, the figure reflects the expected annual economic benefits of improved water quality rather than implementation costs. Differences in methodology mean estimates are not directly comparable but together illustrate the scale and diversity of socio-economic impacts from phosphorus-driven water quality degradation.

	Event	Year	Main nutrient sources	Key impacts	Responses	Cost type	Estimated cost (US\$)
Freshwater Systems	Lake Erie (Toledo Water Crisis), USA	2014	Agricultural runoff (phosphorus fertilisers and manure), wastewater discharges and urban stormwater	Microcystin contamination of municipal drinking water; “Do Not Drink” advisory affecting ~400,000–500,000 residents; closure of businesses and public services	Emergency bottled water distribution; treatment upgrades; improved monitoring; binational phosphorus reduction commitments	Emergency response	≈ US\$65 million ²⁷
	Lake Taihu drinking water crisis, China	2007	Agricultural runoff (phosphorus fertilisers and manure), wastewater discharges and aquaculture	Severe cyanobacterial bloom causing a drinking water crisis affecting ~2 million residents in Wuxi; widespread disruption to municipal water supply	Emergency water supply measures; major wastewater treatment upgrades; large-scale wetland restoration and nutrient reduction programmes	Remediation and restoration investment	≈ US\$2.3 billion ²⁸
	Bangalore Lakes (Bellandur and Varthur), India	Ongoing (major events 2015–2018)	Wastewater discharges (sewage and industrial effluents) and urban stormwater	Persistent algal blooms; toxic foam formation; methane driven lake fires; health risks for surrounding communities	Lake restoration programmes; expansion of sewage treatment plants; regulatory actions	Restoration investment	≈ US\$72 million (based on government restoration funding proposals for Bellandur and Varthur Lakes) ²⁹
	Scottish lochs	Ongoing (2018–present)	Agricultural runoff (phosphorus fertilisers and manure), land runoff, some wastewater discharges	Harmful algal blooms that degrade water quality, reduce recreation and amenity value, harm fisheries, increase water treatment costs, lower property values and pose public health risks	Monitoring programmes; catchment nutrient management; sustainable land management practices	Annual losses from harmful algal blooms	≈ US\$21 million per year (~£16.5 million per year) including higher treatment costs, lost business income and property value declines, with individual outbreaks (e.g., Loch Leven ~US\$2.5 million per year) representative examples ³⁰
Regi	Canadian Lake Erie basin	Scenario modelling (2019 study;	Agricultural runoff (phosphorus fertilisers and manure), wastewater	Increased drinking water treatment costs; reduced tourism and recreation; declining waterfront property values	Nutrient reduction strategies in agriculture; wastewater treatment improvements	Projected damages	≈ US\$3.9 billion over 30 years ³¹

		30 year projection)	discharges and urban stormwater				
	Chesapeake Bay, USA	Ongoing implementation of Total Maximum Daily Load of nutrients (TMDL) since 2010s	Agricultural runoff (phosphorus fertilisers and manure); wastewater discharges; urban stormwater	Eutrophication, harmful algal blooms, hypoxic “dead zones,” loss of fisheries, degraded recreation, reduced water quality	TMDL regulatory limits, watershed implementation plans, agricultural best management practices, wastewater treatment upgrades	Potential ecosystem service gains from improved water quality	≈ US\$22.5 billion per year* to be gained in economic benefits over current conditions ³²
	Lake Victoria Basin, Africa	Ongoing (since 1980s)	Agricultural runoff (fertilisers and livestock waste), untreated urban wastewater and industrial effluents, sediment from upstream land degradation, artisanal mining and aquaculture waste	Algal blooms, water hyacinth proliferation, declining water quality, reduced fish stocks, biodiversity loss, deterioration of livelihoods (fishing, processing, local commerce), increased water-borne disease burden, heightened vulnerability to climate change	Regional coordination, national implementation (infrastructure, monitoring, capacity-building), local engagement (gender-sensitive community programs, livelihood support)	Investment in water quality improvement	≈ US\$10 billion over 10 years for interventions; expected economic benefits include improved livelihoods, health and ecosystem services across the basin ³³
Marine Systems	Beijing Olympics coastal algal bloom, China	2008	Agricultural runoff (phosphorus fertilisers and manure), wastewater discharges and coastal pollution	Large algal bloom affecting ~32% of Olympic sailing venue; ecological damage; disruption to international sporting event	Mobilisation of >10,000 workers; removal of >1 million tonnes of algae; emergency water quality management	Cleanup costs	≈ US\$83 million ³⁴
	Baltic Sea	Ongoing (BSAP implementation since 2000s)	Agricultural runoff (phosphorus and nitrogen), wastewater discharges, industrial discharges	Eutrophication, hypoxic “dead zones,” harmful algal blooms, declines in fisheries and biodiversity	Baltic Sea Action Plan (BSAP); regional nutrient reduction policies; wastewater treatment improvements; agricultural best management practices	Potential ecosystem service gains from improved water quality	≈ US\$4.1 billion per year (willingness-to-pay aggregated across the nine Baltic Sea countries; benefits exceed costs of 2.5–3.2 billion US\$ per year ³⁵

Risks to food security

Phosphorus scarcity and reliance on a few phosphate-rock-rich countries threaten global food security, fertiliser access and economic stability.

Phosphorus is a vital plant nutrient and a key ingredient in fertilisers, making it essential for global food production and food security. Around 90% of the phosphorus applied to agricultural soils comes from mined phosphate rock, rather than recycled sources recovered from waste³⁶. Phosphate rock is a finite and geographically concentrated resource. Around 85% of global phosphate rock reserves are in just five countries: Morocco (70%), China (5%), Egypt (4%), Algeria (3%) and Syria (3%) (Jasinski, 2024). Mining production (i.e. the amount of phosphate rock taken from the ground for use as fertiliser) is similarly concentrated, with China (39%), Morocco (17%), the USA (10%) and Russia (6%) leading global production³⁷.

This concentration leaves the global fertiliser supply chain highly exposed to geopolitical tensions, trade restrictions and supply disruptions. Between 2021 and 2022, phosphorus commodity prices increased by more than 400%, exposing the fragility of global fertiliser supply chains and contributing to the global food price crisis^{38,39}. Key national and global events affecting phosphorus and fertiliser trade during this period included COVID-19-related supply disruptions, China's fertiliser export restrictions, the Russia–Ukraine conflict and associated sanctions, surging fertiliser imports in India, EU trade policies and rising energy and input costs³⁸. Global fertiliser markets have since remained volatile, with a third major price surge emerging in 2025⁴⁰, reflecting continued pressures on supply chains and international trade. Emerging geopolitical tensions, including the 2026 conflict involving Iran and associated increases in energy prices, are placing additional pressure on fertiliser markets and further highlighting the vulnerability of global phosphorus supply chains.

High fertiliser prices can make mineral fertilisers unaffordable for many farmers, particularly in low-income regions. Reduced fertiliser use lowers crop yields and increases the risk of food insecurity^{41,42}. In 2009, it was estimated that around one in seven farmers could not afford sufficient fertiliser to meet crop nutrient needs⁴³. Although more recent global estimates are limited, continued price volatility suggests affordability remains a significant challenge.

The long-term outlook raises further concern. At current extraction rates, known phosphate reserves could be significantly depleted within several decades, although reserve estimates change as new deposits are discovered and economic conditions evolve⁴⁴. Increasing reliance on a small number of supplier countries would heighten geopolitical risks and expose importing nations to potential supply disruptions. For many countries, particularly those dependent on imported fertilisers, phosphorus supply is therefore not only an agricultural issue but also a strategic national security issue for food security. Disruptions to fertiliser supply can affect domestic food production, increase food prices and contribute to wider economic and social instability.

These risks are increasingly recognised in national policy. The United States added phosphate to its list of critical minerals in 2025 and in 2026 invoked defence authorities to secure

elemental phosphorus supplies⁴⁵. The UK Government has also identified fertiliser import dependence and ecosystem degradation as emerging national security risks⁴⁶, while the European Union has listed phosphates as a critical raw material for more than a decade⁴⁷.

Rising fertiliser prices also affect the economics of phosphorus recovery and recycling. As mineral fertiliser prices increase, recovered phosphorus from sources such as manure, food waste and wastewater becomes more economically competitive. Because these resources are generated domestically, recycling systems are less exposed to geopolitical disruptions and global commodity volatility. However, the economic viability of recovery technologies often depends on scale¹⁵. Coordinated national systems that aggregate waste streams and develop markets for recycled fertilisers can significantly improve their feasibility¹². While phosphorus scarcity constrains food production, its excess has equally significant consequences for water systems.

Risks to water security

Excess phosphorus from runoff and wastewater pollutes water, causing algal blooms, biodiversity loss and oxygen-deprived dead zones that threaten ecosystems and drinking water.

Phosphorus is essential for food production, but elevated concentrations in rivers, lakes and coastal waters can severely degrade water quality with severe impacts² (**Figure 3**). The main sources of phosphorus pollution to waters originate from agricultural fertiliser, livestock waste runoff and poorly managed wastewater⁴⁸. In 2015, an estimated 5.5 Mt of phosphorus entered freshwater systems from human activities, with 77 % originating from agriculture, 22 % from sewage and 2 % from aquaculture⁴⁹. These inputs increase the occurrence of harmful algal blooms, degrading water quality, disrupting ecosystem services, threatening human and animal health, reducing biodiversity and generating economic losses² (Table 1).

Although inland waters cover less than 1 % of the Earth's surface, they support approximately 10 % of all species and provide essential ecosystem services, including drinking water supply, food provision, recreation and climate regulation, with an estimated global value of US\$4 trillion annually across all inland waters^{2,50}. Despite their importance, anthropogenic nutrient enrichment affects inland waters across nearly one-third of the planet's terrestrial landmass⁵¹. Approximately one quarter of the global population, over 2 billion people, live in catchments containing inland waters at risk of undesirable algal growth driven by nutrient enrichment⁵¹.

The scale of degradation is evident even in regions with comparatively strong environmental regulation. For example, in the European Union, around 60% of surface waters fail to achieve good ecological status, largely due to nutrient pollution⁵². Such degradation has severe ecological consequences. Globally, freshwater vertebrate populations have declined by approximately 83 % since 1970⁵³ and around one-quarter of freshwater species are now threatened with extinction⁵⁴.

The consequences of freshwater eutrophication also extend beyond inland waters. Decomposition of algal biomass can generate hypoxic “dead zones” in downstream and coastal systems, including the Baltic Sea, Gulf of Mexico and Chesapeake Bay ⁵⁵, as well as large inland systems such as the Laurentian Great Lakes ⁵⁶. These oxygen-depleted areas are unable to support most aquatic life and illustrate the wider global impacts of nutrient pollution. If left unaddressed, continued biodiversity loss could become irreversible, undermining ecosystems on which both people and wildlife depend ⁵⁷. These impacts also extend to the climate system through greenhouse gas emissions associated with eutrophication.

Figure 3. **a)** Two boats floating in an algal bloom in Labelle, Florida, triggered by elevated phosphorus concentrations. Photograph courtesy of Adobe Stock. **b)** Huge harmful algal blooms float towards the coastline of Lake Erie, US, in 2017. Photo Credit: Aerial Associates Photography, Inc. by Zachary Haslick. **c)** An aquaculture farmer cleans away dead fish at a lake in Wuhan, China, 2007. More than 110,000 pounds of fish died due to phosphorus pollution and hot weather in the lake. Photograph courtesy of China Daily/Reuters. **d)** Satellite imagery shows vast algal blooms spreading from the Mississippi River delta into the northern Gulf of Mexico, where nutrient-rich runoff fuels eutrophication and contributes to the seasonal hypoxic “dead zone.” Image courtesy: NASA Earth Observatory / Jeff Schmaltz (MODIS Rapid Response Team, NASA GSFC). **e)** Soldiers’ clear algae along the coastline of Qingdao, Shandong province, in 2008. More than 10,000 people and 1,200 vessels were mobilised to tackle the huge algae bloom that threatened the Olympic sailing event in Qingdao. Photo Credit: Asianewsphoto - Ju Chuanjiang. **f)** A fisherman sets out nets to catch fish in a river heavily polluted by phosphorus in West Bengal, India. Photograph taken by Apratim Pal.

Risks related to climate change

Phosphorus pollution fuels climate change by driving methane emissions from eutrophic lakes, a major but underestimated contributor to global warming, with impacts expected to worsen as temperatures rise.

Phosphorus pollution contributes to climate change, primarily through eutrophication-induced greenhouse gas emissions. Excess phosphorus entering lakes stimulates algal blooms. As the algal biomass dies and decomposes, microbial respiration consumes oxygen and the breakdown of organic matter releases methane. Methane is a potent greenhouse gas with a global warming potential 25 times greater than carbon dioxide³. Methane emissions from eutrophic lakes are estimated to account for up to 20% of fossil fuel-equivalent emissions globally and projections suggest these emissions could double by 2050⁴.

These methane emissions are not fully represented in many global climate models used in assessments by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, which may lead to underestimation of the role phosphorus-driven eutrophication plays in global warming³. Rising global temperatures are expected to increase the frequency and severity of harmful algal blooms, as warmer and more stratified waters favour algal growth and extend bloom seasons. This may further worsen water quality and increase methane emissions. The economic and social costs of methane emissions from phosphorus-polluted lakes are projected to be as much as US\$81 trillion by mid-century⁴. Prioritising sustainable phosphorus management in freshwater ecosystems is essential to mitigating these emissions, protecting biodiversity and addressing the broader climate impacts of nutrient pollution. These interconnected risks highlight the need for coordinated policy responses at national and global levels.

Mapping the global policy landscape

Despite international commitments, phosphorus mismanagement continues to degrade lakes, threatening water security, biodiversity and economies, highlighting the urgent need for stronger global policies and integrated phosphorus governance.

Despite international frameworks like the UN Sustainable Development Goals and the Kunming-Montreal Biodiversity Framework aiming to address global freshwater deterioration, phosphorus, a key driver of water quality degradation, is rarely mentioned. Consequently, progress in tackling the causes and impacts of phosphorus mismanagement remains insufficient. Many of the world's lakes continue to degrade, with reports of ecocide and deliberate infrastructure damage further threatening water security. To avoid further ecosystem degradation, urgent international cooperation is needed to integrate phosphorus management into global sustainability agendas. Prioritising lake restoration and phosphorus

governance is essential to achieving long-term resilience in ecosystems, economies and societies.

Achieving transformative global action for the protection and restoration of ecosystems, including lakes, is essential for maintaining critical ecosystem services. This requires a recognition that many drivers of ecosystem degradation, including those affecting lakes, are global in scope. Despite this, there is currently no comprehensive global policy focused specifically on lake management. Existing policies, where they do exist, typically target local or national scales, such as the USA's Clean Water Act or China's Water Pollution Prevention and Control Action Plan. A few regional policies, like the European Water Framework Directive, have been developed, but they remain exceptions rather than the norm.

Policies for freshwater biodiversity protection are often ineffective, with weak enforcement and limited investment in sustainable lake management. As a result, the biodiversity within many of the world's lakes is frequently overlooked in policy discussions.

Several key global ambitions and international agreements are particularly relevant to lake management and ecosystem restoration, including:

- **The UN Resolution on the Human Right to a Clean, Healthy and Sustainable Environment (A/HRC/RES/48/13)**, which calls on states to enhance environmental protection efforts in fulfilment of human rights obligations and promote international cooperation.
- **The Convention on Biological Diversity's Global Biodiversity Framework 2030**, which includes a target to ensure that 30% of degraded ecosystems are under effective restoration by 2030.
- **The UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDG)**, particularly **SDG 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation)**, which includes targets related to improving water quality, reducing pollution and protecting water-related ecosystems, including lakes.
- **The UN Decade on Ecosystem Restoration (2021–2030)**, led by the United Nations Environment Programme and Food and Agriculture Organization, which promotes global action to prevent, halt and reverse ecosystem degradation, including restoration of freshwater systems.

International recognition of the need for global action on environmental issues affecting lakes is reflected in several UN Environment Assembly (UNEA) Resolutions, such as Resolution 5/4 on Sustainable Lake Management and Resolution 3/10 on Addressing Water Pollution. These resolutions, although non-legally binding, serve as vital steps toward building consensus on global environmental priorities and promoting collective action.

To address these challenges, it is crucial to embed sustainable lake management within the broader landscape of global policy and targets. New indicators for measuring progress, similar to those used in climate change frameworks like the UNFCCC's 1.5 to 2°C targets, could help integrate lake management goals with other global sustainability efforts. The time has come to recognise lakes not just as regional resources, but as integral parts of the global environmental system and to implement policies that reflect their importance in sustaining life and ecosystems worldwide. These interconnected risks highlight the need for coordinated policy responses at national and global scales.

Principles of integration in phosphorus management

To manage phosphorus sustainably, integration across the entire phosphorus cycle is essential, as actions in one stage affect the whole system. Effective management goes beyond phosphorus alone, requiring coordination with other nutrient cycles, local conditions, socio-economic factors, and stakeholder engagement to ensure lasting environmental and resource benefits.

To maintain healthy phosphorus levels in lake waters and wider ecosystems, it is essential to understand phosphorus flows across the entire system, including inputs from land, accumulation in soils and sediments, recovery from waste streams and reuse within agriculture and industry. These flows are influenced by a range of interacting factors, including climate, land use, hydrology, soil characteristics, fertiliser management, policy and regulation, socio-economic conditions, technological capacity and infrastructure.

Phosphorus moves through interconnected stages spanning production, use, loss, recovery and reuse (**Figure 4**). Managing phosphorus in isolation at any one stage is ineffective, as actions in one part of the system directly influence others. For example, reducing phosphorus losses from agricultural land can increase soil phosphorus stocks, requiring adjustments to fertiliser practices to maintain balance and avoid long-term accumulation. Similarly, recovering phosphorus from wastewater or organic wastes only delivers value if it is effectively reintegrated into productive use, such as agriculture. Without this linkage, recovered phosphorus may remain underutilised, limiting progress towards circularity.

This highlights the need for a system-wide approach to phosphorus management. Actions should be designed with the full phosphorus cycle in mind, so that efforts to reduce pollution are aligned with improving resource efficiency, recovery and reuse. Interventions at any stage should be supported by adjustments across the wider system to maximise overall benefits and support progress towards a circular phosphorus system. In this way, improving lake water quality can be achieved alongside wider goals such as nutrient security and circular resource use.

However, integration goes beyond just managing phosphorus within its own cycle. It requires linking phosphorus management with other nutrient cycles and aligning it with broader environmental and policy goals. This wider perspective helps ensure that actions are coordinated and deliver lasting, system-wide benefits.

The following outlines key principles of integrated sustainable phosphorus management (building on those developed for nitrogen management plans; Sutton et al., 2022; Brownlie et al., 2024b), offering critical considerations for guiding policy and practice.

Figure 4. The phosphorus cycle, showing flows of phosphorus between seven (management) stages across the anthropogenic phosphorus cycle: i) phosphate rock mining and mineral fertiliser production, ii) cropping systems, iii) livestock systems, iv) landscape and waterbody management, v) wastewater and solid organic waste management vi) consumers and vii) aquaculture. Not all stages may be present in each lake catchment. A range of measures are available within each group and broken into sub-categories as shown. Selection of measures packages across the system should follow a whole system approach which will be specific for each catchment. Where possible, phosphorus inputs should be minimised, outputs maximised and conditions that favour circularity of phosphorus flows optimised. Importantly, any reduction in phosphorus losses must be matched by a decrease in phosphorus inputs and/or increased outputs.

Key Principle 1. Phosphorus management must address all sources, forms and movement of phosphorus across space and time.

Phosphorus moves through connected stages from use to loss, storage and reuse. It enters agricultural, urban and industrial systems through different pathways and is influenced by land use, climate and infrastructure. Effective management requires understanding where phosphorus is used, where it accumulates and where it is lost. This makes it possible to reduce losses, prevent build-up in soils and water bodies and retain phosphorus within productive use.

Key Principle 2. Reducing phosphorus inputs is key to controlling phosphorus pollution.

Reducing phosphorus inputs at the landscape level reduces phosphorus flow through the entire system, providing opportunities to minimise losses and enhance overall system efficiency. Input reductions should focus on limiting excess fertiliser use, improving nutrient management in agricultural systems and preventing phosphorus-rich runoff. Such measures can help improve the efficiency of phosphorus use in agriculture, without compromising crop yields and may, in some cases, lead to improved economic outcomes.

Key Principle 3. Any reduction in phosphorus losses must be matched by a decrease in phosphorus inputs and/or increased outputs.

Reducing one source of phosphorus pollution may increase phosphorus availability elsewhere in the system unless corresponding measures are applied to balance these reductions (**Figure 5**). For example, reducing phosphorus runoff by adjusting fertiliser application rates must be accompanied by measures to address increased phosphorus accumulation in other parts of the system, such as soil or water bodies. The principle of 'what goes in must come out' applies to all sectors, particularly agriculture, where nutrient flows need to be managed carefully to avoid unintended consequences.

Figure 5. This concept illustrates phosphorus flows within a mixed crop-livestock system. The pink arrows represent phosphorus losses within the landscape, into groundwater, surface waters, or directly into rivers and lakes. While not shown, recycling flows, such as manure and organic waste reuse, play a crucial role in nutrient cycling. Total phosphorus inputs must balance total outputs, accounting for any changes in storage within the system. This framework applies across different

scales, from field and farm levels to regional and global contexts. Importantly, addressing one phosphorus loss pathway can lead to increased phosphorus flow downstream or higher final phosphorus outputs.

Key Principle 4. Managing internal phosphorus loading is critical for restoring lakes with phosphorus-rich sediments.

In lakes with a history of high phosphorus input, sediment-bound phosphorus can be released back into the water column (internal loading), fuelling algal blooms even if external inputs are reduced. Managing this internal loading is often necessary for lake recovery. Measures such as oxygenation, chemical treatment (such as alum) or sediment dredging/removal can reduce release, but they must be combined with reductions in external inputs and improved phosphorus management across the wider system to achieve long-term results.

Key Principle 5. A transition to circular phosphorus systems is needed.

Where possible, phosphorus in waste streams, including manure and sewage sludge, should be recovered and recycled to replace mineral fertiliser inputs. This transition to a circular phosphorus system requires innovative approaches, such as the reuse of phosphorus in agricultural production and may require changes to production systems, including closer integration of livestock and crop systems to facilitate phosphorus recycling. These approaches contribute to the development of both circular and green economies, promoting the sustainable use of phosphorus resources.

Key Principle 6. Co-managing phosphorus with nitrogen and other pollutants enhances water quality outcomes.

Phosphorus and nitrogen pollution share many of the same sources, drivers and impacts, particularly in agricultural settings. As such, efforts to reduce both nitrogen and phosphorus losses can have complementary benefits, addressing multiple nutrient challenges simultaneously. Eutrophication, a shared consequence of nitrogen and phosphorus pollution, results from an imbalance between nutrient inputs and ecosystem capacity. Focusing on both nutrients together ensures a more effective and permanent resolution to these environmental issues.

Key Principle 7. Site-specific management is essential based on local lake and catchment conditions.

Spatial variations in the vulnerability of land to phosphorus losses, the sensitivity of natural habitats and the landscape's capacity to store or buffer phosphorus flows require tailored phosphorus management measures. Factors such as soil type, weather patterns and land management practices influence phosphorus loss pathways. Site-specific approaches, such as precision farming techniques, are essential to optimising phosphorus use efficiency and minimising environmental impacts.

Key Principle 8. Cost-effective solutions and stakeholder involvement are crucial for success.

Phosphorus management must be both affordable and practical for those responsible for implementing changes, such as farmers, municipalities and wastewater treatment operators. Socioeconomic barriers may hinder the implementation of phosphorus mitigation measures, particularly in agriculture. Farmers and landowners may face financial constraints, making it difficult to adopt new practices. Policy frameworks should consider providing financial support, incentives, or access to appropriate resources to facilitate the transition to sustainable phosphorus management.

Key Principle 9. Responsibility for phosphorus management is shared across multiple sectors.

Phosphorus pollution is not just an agricultural or wastewater issue, it requires collaboration between policymakers, land managers, farmers, urban planners and water authorities. A coordinated approach ensures that solutions address the full range of phosphorus sources and impacts. Knowledge exchange and communication between stakeholders will help ensure that strategies are scientifically sound, cost-effective and widely accepted.

Key Principle 10. Trade-offs must be considered when setting priorities.

Reducing phosphorus pollution must balance environmental benefits with economic and social factors. For example, while limiting fertiliser use benefits water quality, it must be done in a way that maintains agricultural productivity. Similarly, expensive lake restoration techniques should be weighed against long-term benefits and alternative strategies. Effective phosphorus management requires flexibility in setting priorities, considering factors such as water quality, ecosystem health and economic outcome.

Designing ‘Measure Packages’

The concept of ‘measure packages’ (as developed for nitrogen management plans; Sutton et al., 2022; Brownlie et al., 2024b) is essential for selecting effective actions to manage phosphorus in lake catchments. These packages should reduce phosphorus inputs, enhance beneficial phosphorus flows (such as plant and microbial uptake) and promote circular phosphorus use to prevent accumulation in water bodies.

Measures must address phosphorus losses across the whole catchment system while avoiding “pollution swapping,” where reducing phosphorus in one area leads to unintended increases elsewhere. For example, reducing fertiliser application may lower runoff but must be paired with actions that prevent phosphorus accumulation in soils or remobilisation from sediments. Importantly, any intervention alters phosphorus cycling dynamics. Changes in land management, wastewater treatment, or in-lake processes can shift nutrient pathways, storage and release. Effective measure packages therefore require ongoing monitoring, cross-sector coordination and adaptive management to refine actions over time.

Circular economy principles should guide planning, including recovery and reuse of nutrients from wastewater, livestock residues and organic waste streams. Successful implementation depends on collaboration across sectors, active stakeholder engagement and alignment with local economic and institutional conditions. Policy instruments can support implementation through a combination of regulatory, economic and advisory approaches, including incentives for nutrient recovery technologies, precision fertilisation, recycled phosphorus use and polluter-pays mechanisms. Capacity building for farmers, water managers and regulators is essential to ensure measures are practical, effective and sustained.

3

A framework for national phosphorus action planning

The Framework for national phosphorus action planning is intended to be used alongside the uPcycle Monitoring and Assessment approach, which provides detailed guidance on implementing its steps. In essence, the Framework outlines what needs to be done, while the Monitoring and Assessment approach offers practical direction on how to carry out these actions.

The Framework for National Phosphorus Action Planning supports the transition to a circular, resource-efficient phosphorus system that protects water quality, strengthens food system resilience and reduces reliance on imported fertilisers. Lake management and restoration remain important applications and indicators of success, but they sit within a broader national strategy that focuses on closing phosphorus loops, recovering nutrients from waste streams and optimising phosphorus use across sectors.

The framework emphasises the importance of integrating environmental protection with resource security, recognising phosphorus as both a pollutant and a finite resource essential for food production. It promotes long-term monitoring systems that track phosphorus flows, recovery rates and system efficiency at regional and national scales. This supports adaptive policymaking in response to changing environmental conditions, technological innovation and shifts in global fertiliser markets or geopolitical supply chains.

Drawing on existing research, including National Sustainable Phosphorus Plans¹³, net-zero phosphorus city approaches⁶⁰ and the Phosphorus Vulnerability Framework¹⁷, the approach supports the development of circular phosphorus systems. Central to this approach is coordinated, cross-sectoral action across the entire phosphorus cycle. ‘Measure packages’ are used to design interventions that achieve multiple goals simultaneously: reducing pollution, restoring ecosystems, improving efficiency and supporting economic value across scales.

This framework is intended for a broad range of stakeholders, including those involved in water management, agriculture, waste and resource management, industry and national policy development. It supports decision-making at multiple scales, from lake catchments to national nutrient strategies.

The framework is structured into four **process levels** that guide the systematic, integrated approach to phosphorus management:

1. **Baseline Assessment**

This stage establishes a comprehensive understanding of the current state of the phosphorus system, including sources, pathways, losses and recovery potential. It gathers evidence on environmental, socio-economic, political and infrastructure conditions, providing the foundation for designing targeted interventions. The baseline creates the context needed to select appropriate strategies and measure packages and identifies opportunities for system-wide improvements and circularity.

2. **Planning**

Building on the baseline, the planning phase translates system understanding into integrated strategies that reduce losses, enhance recovery and improve phosphorus efficiency. It balances environmental, economic and social objectives while considering potential trade-offs and synergies across sectors. Planning defines priorities, aligns interventions with national and local objectives and sets the stage for effective implementation at scale.

3. **Implementation**

In this phase, planned strategies are put into action. Interventions are deployed, coordinated and scaled across the system to reduce losses and promote circular phosphorus flows. Implementation involves operationalising technical, institutional and socio-economic measures while addressing practical challenges. Ongoing monitoring and coordination help maintain coherence across interventions and adapt to emerging issues in real time.

4. **Review and Adaptation**

This stage ensures that phosphorus management remains effective and resilient under changing conditions. Performance is evaluated, lessons are drawn and strategies are adjusted to address emerging environmental, socio-economic and governance challenges. Review and adaptation maintain the long-term relevance of the action plan, support iterative improvement and strengthen the system’s ability to deliver sustainable, circular phosphorus outcomes.

To maintain integration, at each process level, plan developers should assess the role and influence of the six interconnected elements (**Figure 6**). This helps identify needs and opportunities, guiding interventions to maximise benefits and minimise challenges:

1. **Institutions** – Effective governance structures and collaboration mechanisms to ensure coordinated action across stakeholders.
2. **Policies** – Clear, supportive policies that incentivise sustainable phosphorus management and provide regulatory frameworks.
3. **Technologies** – Innovative tools and techniques for managing phosphorus inputs and outputs across the system.
4. **Actors** – Engaging relevant stakeholders, such as farmers, local governments and industry, in the management process.
5. **Information/Knowledge Access** – Ensuring that decision-makers and stakeholders have access to the data and scientific knowledge needed to make informed decisions.
6. **Economics** – Recognising the economic factors that influence decision-making, ensuring that solutions are financially viable and aligned with the interests of stakeholders.

A clear understanding of these elements and their interactions is critical to effective phosphorus management across the catchment. When integrated, they support sustainable, resilient and adaptable strategies that address both environmental and socio-economic challenges.

The following section outlines key questions for each process level. These questions guide the development of an effective and adaptive phosphorus management strategy, ensuring decisions are systematic, informed and aligned with integration principles while addressing phosphorus sources, pathways and impacts across the system.

Figure 6. Illustrative structure of an integrated approach to national phosphorus management. Four process levels, Baseline Assessment, Planning, Implementation and Review and Adaptation, guide systematic action from understanding current conditions to evaluating outcomes and refining strategies. At each stage, there are six interconnected elements, Institutions, Policies, Technologies, Actors, Information/Knowledge Access and Economics, to guide plan developers in assessing roles, influences and requirements. Considering these elements at every process level helps identify opportunities, optimise interventions and ensure sustainable, resilient and adaptable phosphorus management across environmental, socio-economic and governance contexts.

Four **process levels** that guide the systematic, integrated approach to phosphorus management

Six **interconnected elements** guide considerations at each process level

Baseline Assessment

At this stage, the process establishes a comprehensive understanding of phosphorus flows, dependencies and inefficiencies across the national and catchment scale. This includes quantifying inputs, such as fertiliser imports and animal feed, outputs such as crops and livestock products, environmental losses and accumulation in soils and sediments. Both external sources (agricultural runoff, wastewater discharges) and internal cycling (sediment-bound phosphorus, legacy soil stores) are evaluated, particularly where these influence lake or river water quality.

The baseline also identifies recoverable phosphorus in urban, industrial and agricultural waste streams, including wastewater, manure, food waste and by-products from food and industrial sectors. It assesses opportunities to substitute primary phosphorus with recycled sources and considers supply chain vulnerabilities and national dependence on imported fertilisers, informing nutrient security strategies.

Socio-economic conditions, governance structures, institutional capacities, infrastructure readiness and market dynamics are assessed to understand the system's ability to transition towards circular phosphorus management. This stage provides the foundation for designing interventions, selecting appropriate measure packages and anticipating potential trade-offs between environmental, economic and social objectives.

To guide this assessment, the following key questions should be addressed for each of the six interconnected elements:

Interconnected element	Key questions for baseline assessment
Institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What institutions are responsible for phosphorus management, data collection and policy enforcement (e.g., environmental agencies, water utilities, agricultural ministries)? • Are there gaps or overlaps in institutional responsibilities for monitoring phosphorus flows, emissions, land use, soil and water quality? • Who is responsible for collecting and reporting phosphorus data and how accessible is this information to policymakers and the public? • Do institutions have the necessary funding and capacity to implement phosphorus management strategies effectively?
Policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are there existing policies that restrict phosphorus recycling (e.g., bans on using treated organic waste as fertiliser, despite safety approvals)? • Do current subsidies encourage excessive fertiliser use and are there alternative incentive structures to promote efficient phosphorus use? • Are there national, regional, or global phosphorus management targets in place (e.g., EU Water Framework Directive, UN Sustainable Development Goals)? • Are phosphorus management policies aligned with broader climate resilience and biodiversity conservation goals?
Technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What phosphorus recovery and recycling technologies are available for both urban and agricultural systems? • How accessible are recycled fertilisers for agricultural use and what barriers exist for their uptake? • Are there technologies in place to ensure safe and effective manure management, including storage, treatment and application to minimise phosphorus losses? • Do existing biogas plants, composting systems and incineration plants support phosphorus recovery from organic waste streams (e.g., manures, food waste, abattoir residues)? • Are there end-of-waste regulations allowing safe recovered phosphorus products (e.g., struvite, biochar, ash-based fertilisers) to enter the agricultural market? • Are policies in place to promote arable-livestock farm partnerships that enhance phosphorus circularity between manure-producing and crop-growing regions? • Do climate-smart building codes include provisions for source-separated sanitation to facilitate phosphorus recovery in cities? • Does sanitation and wastewater infrastructure allow for safe reuse of water and nutrients to support agriculture? • Do treatment systems consider both phosphorus and nitrogen management to optimise nutrient ratios for reuse while minimising environmental harm? • Are decentralised organic waste treatment infrastructures being planned and do communities support them? • Are there partnerships or knowledge-sharing initiatives between cities and rural areas to improve nutrient recycling systems across different regions? • What lake restoration technologies are available to reduce phosphorus levels and prevent algal blooms? • Are water quality monitoring buoys in place to track phosphorus concentrations and detect early signs of eutrophication? • Is macrophyte management being used effectively to absorb excess nutrients and stabilise sediments? • Can nutrient recovery from aquaculture waste be integrated into phosphorus management strategies? • Are clay amendments or other treatments considered to lock away bioavailable phosphorus in the water column and convert it into non-reactive forms in lake sediments?

Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who are the key stakeholders in phosphorus management (e.g., farmers, landowners, fertiliser manufacturers, wastewater treatment operators, environmental NGOs, tourism industries)? • How do different stakeholder groups influence phosphorus use, recovery and pollution? • Are there existing cross-sector collaborations between agriculture, industry, water utilities and environmental agencies to promote phosphorus sustainability? • What are the barriers to stakeholder engagement and how can participation be improved? • How does phosphorus pollution impact local economies, particularly in communities dependent on lake tourism, aquaculture and recreation? • Are all groups represented fairly and equitably in discussions/actions to deliver better management of phosphorus in the catchment?
Information and Knowledge Access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is phosphorus emissions data publicly available, or is it restricted by private companies? - Are there barriers to data-sharing and communication between institutions (e.g., lack of transparency, proprietary data from private companies)? • Is there third-party verification of industry-reported phosphorus emissions and wastewater discharge data? • Are there monitoring systems in place to track phosphorus inputs, losses and storage across different land uses? • How accessible is scientific knowledge and best practices on phosphorus management to policymakers, landowners and businesses? • Are there partnerships between research institutions and policymakers to improve phosphorus data collection and interpretation?
Economics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the cost burden on water utilities for removing excess phosphorus from drinking water supplies? • Are there economic incentives for industries and farmers to adopt phosphorus recovery technologies? • How do market forces influence phosphorus prices and how might price fluctuations affect phosphorus management efforts? • Are there industries aligned with a circular phosphorus economy (e.g., eco-tourism, nutrient recovery businesses, recycled fertiliser manufacturers) that need policy or financial support? • What cross-sector engagement is required to support a transition to circular phosphorus flows? • What are the human health risks associated with phosphorus-driven toxic algal blooms and how might these affect economic sectors such as public health and tourism? • What are the risks of greenhouse gas emissions from eutrophic water bodies, particularly methane and nitrous oxide releases from decomposing algal blooms?

Planning

Building on the baseline, the planning phase focuses on designing integrated strategies that reduce phosphorus losses, enhance recovery and improve system efficiency. Planning aligns environmental objectives, such as lake restoration and ecosystem protection, with broader goals including reduced dependence on imported fertilisers, improved nutrient use efficiency and the development of circular phosphorus systems. Interventions are developed through stakeholder engagement and are underpinned by scientific evidence and economic analysis. Strategies consider trade-offs between sectors, coordinate phosphorus management with other nutrient cycles and ensure actions are practical, scalable and economically viable. Policy, regulatory and market frameworks are considered to support the uptake of recycled phosphorus, including incentives, infrastructure development and supply chain measures.

To guide planning, the following key questions should be considered for each of the six interconnected elements:

Interconnected Elements	Key questions for planning
Institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How can institutional roles and responsibilities be restructured or clarified to ensure effective implementation of phosphorus management strategies? • What institutional collaborations (e.g., between government agencies, researchers, water utilities, industry) are needed to support phosphorus reduction and recovery? • What governance mechanisms (e.g., regulatory frameworks, advisory boards, inter-agency task forces) can be established or improved to oversee long-term phosphorus management?
Policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What policy changes are needed to enable phosphorus reduction and recovery (e.g., removing regulatory barriers to recycled phosphorus use, adjusting agricultural subsidies)? • How can new or revised policies align with national and international water quality, climate and circular economy goals? • What enforcement mechanisms and incentives (e.g., fines, subsidies, tax breaks) are needed to drive compliance with phosphorus management policies?
Technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Based on baseline findings, what phosphorus management technologies should be prioritised for implementation (e.g., recovery from wastewater, improved fertiliser efficiency, in-lake interventions)? • What infrastructure upgrades or investments are required to deploy these technologies effectively? • What capacity-building programs (e.g., training, technical support) are necessary to ensure stakeholders can adopt and use these technologies?
Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How can key stakeholders (e.g., farmers, wastewater managers, water companies, landowners) be engaged in the planning and implementation process? • What partnerships (e.g., public-private collaborations, research-industry alliances) can be formed to enhance phosphorus management outcomes? • How can community-level engagement be fostered to encourage local participation in phosphorus reduction efforts?
Information and Knowledge Access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What new data collection and monitoring systems should be introduced to track phosphorus levels and intervention success? • How can real-time data and digital tools (e.g., GIS mapping, remote sensing, monitoring buoys) be integrated into phosphorus management plans? • What knowledge-sharing platforms (e.g., workshops, online databases, advisory networks) are needed to improve decision-making and ensure best practices are disseminated?
Economics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the estimated costs and economic trade-offs of different phosphorus management interventions? • What financial mechanisms (e.g., subsidies, market incentives, public-private funding) can support phosphorus recovery and circular economy initiatives? • How can cost-sharing agreements be structured to distribute financial responsibility fairly among stakeholders (e.g., water utilities, farmers, municipalities)?

Implementation

The Implementation phase translates plans into action by operationalising strategies across the six interconnected elements. Its goal is to reduce system-wide phosphorus losses and scale circular phosphorus practices. Interventions are designed to be practical, effective and evidence based. Establishing and supporting long-term monitoring systems is central to this phase. These systems provide data to assess intervention effectiveness, maintain an understanding of baseline conditions and support adaptive management.

Interventions are developed through stakeholder engagement and are underpinned by scientific evidence and economic analysis. This includes deploying policies that support phosphorus reduction and recovery, introducing technologies for nutrient capture and recycling and integrating these into existing infrastructure. Interventions are tailored to be accessible, well-maintained and appropriate for local conditions.

Effective implementation requires coordination across all sectors of the phosphorus value chain. Farmers, water utilities, industry, waste managers and policymakers must work together to ensure actions are aligned and mutually reinforcing. Capacity building, training, knowledge transfer and advisory support help stakeholders adopt circular practices and technologies. Financial mechanisms such as subsidies, incentives and investment frameworks support the development of phosphorus recovery infrastructure and circular business models.

Adaptive management is central to this phase. Interventions are regularly reviewed to respond to changing environmental conditions, stakeholder behaviour and technological performance. Monitoring data, stakeholder feedback and system-wide assessments help identify misalignments, address emerging challenges and refine strategies. This ensures benefits are maximised across the entire phosphorus cycle and supports the transition to circular and sustainable systems.

To guide implementation, the following key questions should be addressed for each of the six interconnected elements:

Interconnected Elements	Key questions for implementation
Institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How can institutional coordination be improved to ensure smooth implementation of phosphorus management strategies across various sectors and agencies? • Are responsible agencies equipped with the necessary resources (e.g., funding, staffing, expertise) and authority to enforce phosphorus-related policies and regulations effectively? • How will institutions track progress and adapt strategies if initial phosphorus management approaches are found to be ineffective or insufficient in improving lake water quality? • What mechanisms will be used to ensure effective communication and collaboration between agencies during the implementation process?
Policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How will compliance with new phosphorus management policies (e.g., nutrient reduction targets, treatment standards) be monitored and what are the penalties for non-compliance? • What enforcement mechanisms (e.g., fines, reporting requirements, financial incentives) will be put in place to ensure adherence to phosphorus reduction and recovery regulations? • Are the policies being implemented in a way that aligns with broader environmental, economic and social goals, such as improving water quality, supporting a circular economy, or contributing to net-zero emission strategies? • How will policies be adjusted if they are found to be ineffective or in conflict with other regional or national environmental objectives?
Technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How will the planned phosphorus management technologies (e.g., wastewater treatment systems, sediment remediation technologies, nutrient capture systems) be deployed effectively and at scale? • What maintenance, monitoring and support systems will be necessary to ensure these technologies remain functional, efficient and sustainable over time? • How will technology users (e.g., farmers, wastewater treatment operators, industries) be trained to operate and optimise these systems, ensuring that they are used properly and effectively? • How will new technologies be integrated into existing infrastructure and what steps will be taken to ensure compatibility with local needs and conditions?
Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How will stakeholders (e.g., local communities, industries, farmers, government bodies) be supported and incentivised to take an active role in phosphorus management interventions and adhere to policies? • What mechanisms are in place to resolve conflicts or disagreements between stakeholders (e.g., landowners vs. regulatory bodies, urban vs. rural interests) to ensure smooth implementation of phosphorus management actions? • How will community engagement, outreach and education efforts be maintained throughout the implementation process to ensure broad public support and participation? • How will the roles and responsibilities of various stakeholders be communicated and clarified to avoid misunderstandings and ensure accountability?
Information and Knowledge Access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How will data on phosphorus levels, pollution sources and the success of interventions be collected, monitored and shared in real-time to support adaptive management? • What systems will be established to ensure that decision-makers and key stakeholders have continuous access to up-to-date, actionable information to guide their actions? • How will knowledge-sharing across sectors (e.g., agriculture, wastewater, urban planning and environmental management) be facilitated to improve phosphorus management practices and outcomes? • What tools or platforms will be used to track and disseminate knowledge about phosphorus management strategies, best practices and lessons learned?

Economics

- How will the implementation phase of phosphorus management be funded and what financial support mechanisms (e.g., grants, subsidies, private sector investments) will be utilised to sustain phosphorus interventions in the long term?
- Are there mechanisms in place to adjust funding strategies or reallocate resources if economic conditions change or unforeseen challenges arise during the implementation phase?
- How will cost-sharing models be enforced to ensure fairness among stakeholders, balancing the financial burden between government agencies, industries, farmers and local communities?
- How can the financial sustainability of phosphorus management efforts be ensured, particularly in the face of potential budget constraints or shifts in funding priorities?

Review and Adaptation

The review and adaptation stage ensures that phosphorus management continues to reduce losses, improve lake and catchment outcomes and remain effective under changing environmental, economic and governance conditions.

Long-term monitoring is essential. It helps detect emerging phosphorus sources, delayed responses in the system and unintended consequences of interventions. These insights allow interventions to be adjusted to prevent trade-offs or new environmental pressures. Evaluations also consider effectiveness, cost efficiency, equity and broader system impacts to ensure improvements in one area do not create problems elsewhere.

Stakeholder engagement is revisited during this phase. Policies, governance arrangements and funding mechanisms may need updating to reflect new priorities or changing conditions. At the same time, incorporating the latest scientific evidence and technological advances strengthens circular phosphorus practices and supports iterative improvement. This approach keeps management aligned with national priorities, promotes nutrient security and maintains long-term sustainability.

To guide this process, the following key questions should be considered for each of the six interconnected elements:

Interconnected Elements	Key questions for review and adaption
Institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are institutional roles and responsibilities for phosphorus management in the lake catchment clearly defined and have they been effective in achieving water quality goals? • What gaps or inefficiencies have emerged in the governance structures related to phosphorus management and how can these be addressed to improve lake water quality outcomes? • Is there a process in place to integrate lessons learned from previous phosphorus management actions into future strategies? How can these lessons be shared across relevant stakeholders? • How can inter-agency coordination and collaboration be improved to enhance the management of phosphorus pollution at the lake and catchment scale?
Policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have phosphorus management policies (e.g., nutrient reduction targets, wastewater treatment regulations) achieved their intended outcomes in improving lake water quality, or do they require modification? • Are there any unintended consequences (e.g., pollution swapping, economic burdens) from the existing policies that need to be addressed to avoid compromising lake health? • How can policy enforcement mechanisms be improved to ensure compliance with phosphorus reduction and recovery measures? • Are there opportunities to align phosphorus policies with broader environmental goals (e.g., water quality targets, ecosystem health, climate adaptation strategies) to maximise overall effectiveness? • What additional policies or regulatory frameworks are needed to address emerging challenges in phosphorus management, such as agricultural runoff or urban pollution?
Technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are the phosphorus management technologies currently deployed in the lake (e.g., water treatment, sediment remediation, algae control) performing as expected? Are there any areas for improvement? • Have any technological failures or inefficiencies been identified and how can they be corrected to improve phosphorus reduction or recovery efforts? • What new or emerging technologies (e.g., precision agriculture, phosphorus recovery from wastewater, advanced monitoring systems) could enhance phosphorus management and reduce its impact on lake water quality? • How can the scalability and sustainability of existing or new technologies be ensured, particularly considering local conditions, costs and infrastructure readiness?
Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have all relevant stakeholders (e.g., farmers, local businesses, water utilities, government bodies) been effectively engaged in phosphorus management activities? What additional stakeholders should be involved? • What barriers to stakeholder participation have emerged during phosphorus management efforts and how can they be overcome to ensure greater involvement in future initiatives? • How can collaboration and partnerships among stakeholders be strengthened to ensure long-term success in phosphorus management and lake water quality improvements? • How can local communities and industries be incentivised to participate in phosphorus reduction and recovery efforts? • Are there mechanisms in place to resolve conflicts between stakeholders (e.g., landowners vs. regulatory bodies, urban vs. rural areas) and ensure shared responsibility for phosphorus management?

Information and Knowledge Access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is phosphorus monitoring data being collected and shared effectively to inform decision-making and track progress towards phosphorus reduction goals? • Are there any gaps in monitoring and data collection that need to be addressed, particularly regarding sources of phosphorus pollution or intervention effectiveness? • How can data-sharing between stakeholders (e.g., local agencies, water utilities, farmers) be improved to ensure transparency and avoid duplication of efforts? • How can research findings and monitoring data be translated into practical, actionable guidance for decision-makers in the lake catchment area? • What knowledge-sharing platforms (e.g., workshops, online databases, community networks) need to be developed or strengthened to facilitate better decision-making and improve best practice dissemination?
Economics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have the financial resources allocated for phosphorus management in the lake been sufficient? Are there opportunities to increase funding or allocate resources more efficiently to meet phosphorus reduction targets? • What are the estimated costs of implementing phosphorus management strategies (e.g., technology deployment, policy enforcement, community engagement) and how can these be minimised or optimised? • What financial mechanisms (e.g., grants, subsidies, market incentives, tax incentives) can be used to support phosphorus recovery, reduction technologies and sustainable practices across the catchment? • Are existing cost-sharing models (e.g., between government, industries, farmers) fair and sustainable and do they effectively distribute the financial burden of phosphorus management? • How can the economic impact of phosphorus pollution on lake ecosystems, water quality and local economies be measured and communicated to stakeholders to support continued investment in management efforts? • How can financial strategies be adapted to ensure long-term resilience and cost-effectiveness in phosphorus management, particularly in the face of changing economic conditions or funding availability?

Conclusion

The uPcycle Phosphorus Framework provides a structured approach to help governments and national authorities develop effective National Phosphorus Action Plans. The complementary uPcycle Monitoring and Assessment approach offers practical guidance and links to a wide range of technical tools to support plan development, implementation and adaptation. These resources provide a strong technical foundation, enabling plans to be developed today. However, political legitimacy, formal endorsement and institutional backing are decisive for translating plans into real-world action.

High-level global commitments reflect growing recognition that sustainable phosphorus management, alongside other nutrients, is urgently required. For example, the Executive Director of the United Nations Environment Programme used the 2025 Priorities for a Resilient Planet report to urge Member States to establish national working groups on sustainable nutrient management, with “a greater focus on phosphorus, in particular,” to provide guidance ahead of UNEA-8⁶¹. Experience from climate governance shows that ambitious national action often precedes international progress⁶². Early national implementation builds political momentum, demonstrates feasibility and creates conditions for multilateral cooperation.

National drivers for phosphorus action differ. In some countries, the priority is national security, ensuring reliable phosphorus access and food system resilience, while in others the focus is on protecting lakes and water bodies. While these represent top-down drivers for action, the solutions are often the same; what differs is how they are framed and communicated. However, effective implementation depends on bottom-up approaches that reflect stakeholder realities. Understanding stakeholder challenges and providing clear guidance, technical support and financial resources is essential to translate plans into real-world outcomes.

The development of effective phosphorus management strategies is an ongoing process that builds on existing plans and is refined through iterative improvements. While a perfect plan may not be achievable initially, continual adaptation and collaboration improve outcomes over time. This framework explicitly anticipates that plans will evolve through evaluation, adjustment and learning. Long-term monitoring and assessment generate data to track progress, detect emerging trends and guide necessary changes. This systematic, adaptive approach strengthens nutrient security, reduces phosphorus pollution and supports resilience in ecosystems, economies and communities.

For additional resources and tools, visit the uPcycle Hub at www.upcycle.org.

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National Phosphorus Action Planning

A Framework for addressing the global phosphorus challenge to protect rivers, lakes and coastlines

Phosphorus is essential for food production, yet its mismanagement threatens water quality, ecosystem health, climate mitigation and long-term resource security. Addressing this challenge is critical for sustainable food systems, environmental protection and national resilience. This document provides a practical framework to support the development of National Phosphorus Action Plans, emphasising integrated, system-wide action to transition towards circular phosphorus use. It guides countries through a structured process, including assessing phosphorus flows and pressures, identifying priorities, selecting coordinated measures and supporting implementation and review.

Developed through the uPcycle project, funded by the Global Environment Facility (GEF) in coordination with the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), this framework supports effective, joined-up action to protect water resources while ensuring sustainable phosphorus use.

 uPcycle